

Deliverable: 2.1

Title: Report from the study visits

Project information

Project Title	Networking for excellence in the development of innovative, consumer-oriented horticultural food products using the Living Lab approach
Acronym:	HortiFoodTrends
Grant agreement:	101159293
Topic	HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ACCESS-02-01 - Twinning Bottom-Up
Type of action	Horizon - Coordination and Support Action
Granting authority	European Research Executive Agency
Start date of the project	1 June 2024
Duration	36 months
Project Coordinator	Monika Mieszczakowska-Frąc
Project Website	www.hortifoodtrends.eu

Deliverable information

Deliverable title	Report from the study visits
Deliverable number	2.1
Deliverable version	1.0
Work Package	WP2 - Capacity-building towards Living-Lab approach in novel food design
Contractual date of delivery	M17 - 31/10/2025
Actual date of delivery	M17 - 30/10/2025
Deliverable type:	R – Document, report
Responsible Partner	LYFE

Authoring & Approval

Authors	Alexia Jauniau
Reviewers	Ronan Symoneaux, Michael Bom Frøst, Agnès Giboreau
Approved for submission	Monika Mieszczakowska-Frąc

Dissemination level

PU	Public, fully open, e.g. web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page)	X
SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	
Classified R-UE/EU-R	EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444	
Classified C-UE/EU-C	EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444	
Classified S-UE/EU-S	UE/EU-S – EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444	

Document History

Version	Date	Description of Change
V0.1	27/10/2025	First draft
V0.2	29/10/2025	Second draft version incorporating 1 review comment
V0.3	30/10/2025	Final draft send to PC
V1.0	30/10/2025	Final version submitted to EC by the PC

Disclaimer

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Innovation programme under grant agreement No 101159293. Disclaimer: This report only reflects the views of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. The European Commission is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

Configuration Management: Document Location

The latest version of this controlled document is stored in [D2.1 Report from the study visits](#).

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The deliverable 2.1 “Report from the study visits” describes the outcomes of a series of targeted study visits conducted as part of Work Package 2 (WP2), which focused on training in Living Lab practices, Food Design thinking (Task 2.1) with culinary development and co-creation, sensory and consumer research (Task 2.2) , and consumer eating behaviour (Task 2.1) . Led by LYFE (France), the University of Copenhagen (UCPH, Denmark), and GROUPE ESA (France), the project facilitated three one-month internship periods for researchers from InHort (Poland), corresponding to each Task. These visits aimed to build practical expertise in sensory analysis, consumer research methodologies, Living Lab organisation, and advanced data analysis.

The internships were carried out in two- or three-person teams, with at least one participant holding the status of an Early Stage Researcher. To increase the possibility of mobility for people with families, internships were organised in a 2-week trip. In this way, 6 internships were held as part of WP2, in which 7 researchers from InHort participated, including 4 ESRs. After completing the internship, each team shared the knowledge they acquired during an organised seminar at InHort.

1. INTRODUCTION

WP2, led by LYFE, focused on training in Living Lab practices, Food Design thinking, sensory and consumer research, and consumer cooking and eating behaviour.

UCPH (University of Copenhagen) led Task 2.1 (M1-M17) by offering one-month internships for two InHort researchers at UCPH's Department of Food Science in Denmark. The interns gained hands-on experience in sensory and consumer research, working with Danish panellists and data analysis.

Task 2.2, led by LYFE (France), involved two InHort researchers completing one-month internships at LYFE's Living Lab facility. They learnt about Living Lab organisation, experimental restaurant/kitchen management, culinary development, and advanced methodology to understand consumer perception. The program included participation in a joint research project, covering experiment design, qualitative research organisation, consumer recruitment, logistics, video analysis, data analysis, and report writing.

Task 2.3, led by GROUPE ESA and LYFE, provided three InHort Sensory Panel Leaders with a one-month internship (split between GROUPE ESA and LYFE). The focus was on organising sensory and consumer tests, including panellist selection, training, and management, with a specific emphasis on working with elderly target groups at ESA. At GROUPE ESA, they learnt advanced data analysis for QDA. At the same time, at LYFE, the training covered quantitative research and a specific part on consumer language (open comment) in real-life consumer testing.

Key achievements included:

- The development and sensory profiling of innovative berry-based products, such as aronia coulis and chokeberry cheesecakes, validated through consumer feedback and statistical analysis.
- The successful application of qualitative and quantitative research methodologies, including focus groups, usage tests, and large-scale consumer evaluations, enhanced InHort's capacity for consumer-led innovation.
- The presentation of findings at the Pangborn Congress (2025), showcasing the Living Lab process as a bridge between sensory research, culinary creativity, and market readiness for underutilised berries.

The project also addressed challenges such as panellist recruitment delays, recipe adaptation for French consumers, and questionnaire design, mitigating them through flexible scheduling, pre-testing, and extended data-collection periods. Recommendations for future initiatives include advancing ingredient preparation for co-creation sessions, shortening questionnaires, and maintaining adaptable timelines to ensure robust participant engagement.

Overall, the study visits significantly strengthened InHort's methodological and analytical capabilities, fostering confidence and collaboration among researchers. The integration of sensory science, consumer insights, and culinary innovation demonstrated the value of a consumer-inclusive approach in transforming underutilised berries into market-ready products, paving the way for further EU-level development and commercialisation opportunities.

2. OVERVIEW OF CONDUCTED STUDY VISITS

Researchers, PhD students, and technical staff from InHort were travelling to the 3 partners' facilities to gain knowledge and acquire new skills.

Study Visit ID	Host Institution	Visiting Institution	Key objective	Dates	Duration	# Participants	Deviations (yes/no)
T2.1 SV-001	UCPH (Denmark)	InHort	Methods and techniques used in sensory and consumer tests and data analysis.	19.05- 30.05.2025	2 weeks	A.Wrzodak	No
						D.Wieloch	
T2.1 SV-002	UCPH (Denmark)	InHort		31.03- 11.04.2025	2 weeks	K.Celejewska	No
						J.Piecko	
T2.2 SV-001	LYFE (France)	InHort	Living Lab organisation to study cooking and eating behaviours in real life situations.	20- 31.01.2025	2 weeks	S.Siarkowski	No
						D.Wieloch	
T2.2 SV-002	LYFE (France)	InHort		21.07- 1.08.2025	2 weeks	A.Wrzodak	Yes
						M. Mieszczakowska-Frac	
T2.3 SV-001	ESA (France)	InHort	Advanced data analysis for QDA.	16- 27.06.2025	2 weeks	A Wrzodak	No
						K.Celejewska	
						D.Wieloch	
T2.3 SV-002	LYFE (France)	InHort	Consumers language and real-life testing with consumers.	12.05- 23.05.2025	2 weeks	S.Siarkowski	No
						J.Piecko	
						J.Zdulski	

3. SUMMARY OF KEY ACHIEVEMENTS & IMPACT

Study Visit ID	Description of key skill/knowledge/contribution 1	Description of key skill/knowledge/contribution 2	Description of key skill/knowledge/contribution 3
T2.1 - SV-001	QDA (aronia coulis)	Projective Mapping (aronia/vegetable pastes)	
T2.1 - SV-002	QDA (haskap/ strawberry purees)	Projective Mapping (dried cranberries)	
T2.2 - SV-001	Qualitative research with consumers	Co-creation recipe development and culinary session	Sensory description with consumers in qualitative research
T2.2 - SV-002	Usage research with consumers and execution	Behavioural observation of consumers	
T2.3 - SV-001	Consumer Testing & Sensory Evaluation	Specialised Research Methodologies	Data Analysis & Reporting
T2.3 - SV-002	Quantitative research with consumers	Data and open-ended question analysis	Data Analysis & Reporting

NOTE on PANGBORN Poster:

T2.2 - SV-001 and T2.3 - SV-002 living labs and training contents have been used to develop and present a poster at the Pangborn Congress in August 2025 in Philadelphia. The poster focuses on each step of the project: qualitative research with consumers on ingredients and recipes ideation, culinary development and sensory qualitative feedback from consumers, recipe selection and quantitative research to get consumers' feedback.

The conclusion is that this Living Lab process demonstrates the value of combining qualitative phases with consumers and culinary creativity with chefs to link food habits and preferences with new ingredients, providing concrete recipes and berry usage to be further pursued at the EU level. Living Lab collaboration bridges sensory, technological, and commercial gaps — boosting innovation and uptake.

The project confirms that a consumer-inclusive approach is essential for turning underutilised berries into accepted, functional, and market-ready products to get closer to a commercialisation opportunity to be developed for the Polish berries.

See the Pangborn poster in

Annexes.

3.1. Study visit 1 (T2.1 - SV-001) – Key skills and knowledge acquired

T2.1 - SV-001	QDA (aronia coulis)	Projective Mapping (aronia/vegetable pastes)
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Visiting researchers and UCPH conducted **QDA on aronia coulis** and **projective mapping for aronia/vegetable pastes**, refining sensory analysis techniques and establishing precise product profiles. This collaboration **strengthened InHort’s methodological capabilities**, developed **new prototypes for WP4**, and opened avenues for **future joint research** on these products.

3.1.1. QDA (aronia coulis)

- **QDA (aronia coulis):** Quantitative Descriptive Analysis (QDA) using a set of developed aronia coulis as test objects
- **Enhancements in project methodologies:** The visitor researchers worked with UCPH sensory panel leaders on training the panel for QDA following state-of-the-art methodology. Jointly they executed a full descriptive analysis of a set of aronia coulis developed in the project. Together with the UCPH-host researcher, they analysed the resulting data, both for product differences, as well as descriptor and panellist quality following best practice data reporting. Finally, they prepared the data to describe relationships to instrumental measurements that will be carried out in InHort. The activity thus enhances InHort capacities for this methodology.
- **New research directions initiated:** The new research from this activity is a precise descriptive profile, of the experimental coulis developed during T2.2 SV-001 stay as part of the research in WP4.
- **Potential for future collaboration:** In the future work in WP4, some of the research will build on the aronia coulis.

3.1.2. Projective Mapping (aronia/vegetable pastes)

- **Projective mapping (aronia/vegetable pastes):** Executing a fast sensory profile of aronia/vegetable pastes with Projective mapping techniques
- **Enhancements in project methodologies:** The visitor researchers worked with UCPH host researcher to develop a fast sensory profile of aronia/vegetable pastes. Jointly they analysed the resulting data clarifying ambiguous descriptors from the panelists and reporting main product differences following best practice data reporting. The activity thus enhances InHort capacities for this methodology.
- **New research directions initiated:** The aronia/vegetable pastes are new prototypes developed as part of WP4, and further optimisation of the recipes will be carried out in WP4.
- **Potential for future collaboration:** The visiting researchers can carry out projective mapping on their own, but both parties will benefit from joint research using the methodology.

3.2. Study visit 2 (T2.1 - SV-002) – Key skills and knowledge acquired

T2.1 - SV-002	QDA (haskap/ strawberry purees)	Projective Mapping (dried cranberries)
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Researchers applied **QDA** to haskap/strawberry purees—including ultrasonic treatment effects—and **projective mapping** to dried cranberries, comparing InHort’s **prototypes** with **commercial** products. These efforts expanded **sensory research** and will result in a **joint publication**.

3.2.1. QDA (haskap/ strawberry purees)

- Quantitative Descriptive Analysis (QDA) using a set of developed haskap/strawberry purees as test objects.
- The enhancement of methodologies capacity is the same as T2.1 - SV – 001, but the specific research is carried out on a different set of samples developed for research at InHort.
- **New research directions initiated:** The activity initiates research on the sensory properties of haskap purees, alone and mixed with strawberry purees. The sample set, in addition, investigated the effect of ultrasonic treatment during the puree process, characterised both by sensory and instrumental methods.
- **Potential for future collaboration:** The visit will result in a joint publication on the topic.

3.2.2. Projective Mapping (dried cranberries)

- Projective mapping technique execution and data analysis using a selection of dried cranberries as test objects
- **Enhancements in project methodologies:** The enhancement of methodologies capacity is the same as T2.1 - SV – 001, but the specific research is carried out on a different set of samples (dried cranberries) developed at InHort that is compared to commercially available products in Denmark.

3.3. Study visit 3 (T2.2 - SV-001) – Key skills and knowledge acquired

T2.2 - SV-001	Qualitative research with consumers	Co-creation recipe development and culinary session	Sensory description with consumers in qualitative research
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At LYFE, a **focus group** was organised to explore ingredient pairings using InHort’s processed ingredients, resulting in the selection of **8 potential recipe concepts** featuring chokeberry and haskap berry.

LYFE’s chefs then developed and refined these ideas into **4 final recipes – co-creation culinary session-**, which were tested and adjusted based on feedback from InHort visitors. A **second focus group** was conducted to gather detailed consumer feedback.

Using **tasting sheets with sensory descriptors**, consumers evaluated the recipes, identifying strengths, weaknesses, and areas for improvement. This collaborative process enabled **in-depth discussions** between researchers and consumers on the sensory qualities of berry-based recipes.

3.3.1. Qualitative research with consumers

- The 1st step at LYFE was the organisation of a focus group, including InHort processed ingredients, presented to consumers. The objective of the qualitative research was to imagine possible pairing with other ingredients in some recipes, by discussion and projection of sensory characteristics of ingredients.
- 8 different potential recipes leads were discussed and selected to move forward to the next step.

- After the co-creation recipe development and culinary session, another step of qualitative research has been carried out.

3.3.2. Co-creation recipe development and culinary session

- The focus group session led to a co-creation of 8 food concepts with consumers, including chokeberry and haskap berry.
- Then, the LYFE chefs involved in the project have developed various food concepts based on consumers' idea, and 4 were selected.
- The 4 recipes were developed, adjusted and proposed to be tasted by InHort visitors to adjust and correct as needed.
- After that, a 2nd focus group was run with consumers.

3.3.3. Sensory description with consumers in qualitative research

- During the 2nd step of qualitative research, consumers tasted the recipes and provided feedback on potential improvements.
- To provide feedback in an efficient way, tasting sheets with sensory descriptors were provided to collect strengths and weaknesses of each recipe; sensory attributes measurement and improvement lead identified.
- The qualitative research allowed a discussion between InHort researchers and consumers on sensory perspectives of recipes based on berries.

3.4. Study visit 4 (T2.2 - SV-002) – Key skills and knowledge acquired

T2.2 - SV-002	Usage research with consumers and execution	Behavioural observation of consumers
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During **Task 2.2 (T2.2 - SV-002)**, InHort developed **aronia- and vegetable-based spreads**, and LYFE organised a **consumer usage test**—including pre-tests and dry runs—to observe how consumers paired the spreads with various side foods, identifying the most complementary combinations.

Consumer behaviour was closely monitored through **direct observation and video recording**, capturing actions like the order of food selection, usage of side foods, and sensory interactions (e.g., smelling before tasting).

The test combined **declarative questions and observational data**, including consumer preferences for two specific spreads, to provide a comprehensive understanding of usage patterns and product appeal.

3.4.1. Usage research with consumers and execution

- InHort developed products, spreads (pastes, tartinables) based on aronia and vegetables and few spices.
- To allow understanding of how consumers would eat the spreads, an usage test with consumer was organized at LYFE, with pre-test and dry run to make sure the methodology was adapted to the objective.
- Different side foods were presented, and the choice to be made by consumers to understand which ones are the most useful and goes the best with the pastes.

3.4.2. Behavioural observation of consumers

- To record behaviour of consumers during the test, direct observation was made and reported to note down the consumers' choices and usage of the side food (which order, did they use the 3 of them...)
- Additionally, hands video recording allowed to catch up the other gestures of consumers during the test, such as smelling before tasting...
- The test was using declarative questions and observation, including liking question on 2 pastes (spreads).

3.5. Study visit 5 (T2.3 - SV-001) – Key skills and knowledge acquired

T2.3 - SV-001	Consumer Testing & Sensory Evaluation	Specialised Research Methodologies	Data Analysis & Reporting
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During Task 2.3 (T2.3 - SV-001), researchers designed and executed large-scale consumer tests (100+ participants), managing recruitment, logistics, and sensory evaluations for product pairings while working with expert panels to ensure robust data collection.

They applied specialised methodologies, including Eco Consumer Led Innovation and adapted testing for elderly consumers across diverse environments (labs, homes, nursing homes), ensuring compliance with Good Laboratory Practices (GLP).

Finally, they conducted statistical analyses of consumer data and produced targeted reports to address the research objectives.

3.5.1. Consumer Testing & Sensory Evaluation

- Designing and implementing consumer tests, including pre-test and logistics (setup, execution, cleanup).
- Managing consumer databases and recruitment processes.
- Conducting large-scale sensory evaluations (e.g., 100+ participants for product pairings like coulis with madeleines and fromage blanc).
- Working with expert sensory panels, including recruitment, motivation, and performance assessment.

3.5.2. Specialised Research Methodologies

- Applying Eco Consumer Led Innovation principles to product testing and development.
- Adapting testing methodologies for specific demographics, particularly elderly consumers.
- Conducting tests in varied environments (laboratory, home, nursing homes).
- Ensuring compliance with Good Laboratory Practices (GLP) for standardized and reproducible testing.

3.5.3. Data Analysis & Reporting

- Analysing and interpreting consumer test data, including statistical evaluation of results.
- Reporting redaction and oriented toward answering the objective.

3.6. Study visit 6 (T2.3 - SV-002) – Key skills and knowledge acquired

T2.3 - SV-002	Quantitative research with consumers	Data and open-ended question analysis	Data Analysis & Reporting
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A real-meal quantitative test was conducted at LYFE Institute’s restaurant, where 70 consumers evaluated two cheesecake recipes over two weeks. The study validated sensory improvements, revealing that increased chokeberry content did not affect overall liking—though acidity and sweetness balance were noted—while crispy apple chips were highly appreciated. InHort supported questionnaire design, data collection, analysis, and reporting.

PhD researchers were trained in analysing open-ended consumer feedback, learning to extract key terms, create contingency tables, and present findings effectively.

The team also performed statistical analysis of consumer data and produced focused reports to address the research objectives.

3.6.1. Quantitative research with consumers

- In the selected food concept with consumers and execution in a real meal situation at the restaurant of the LYFE Institute.
- A monadic pure hedonic quantitative test on 2 versions of the cheesecake recipe in real meal situations was run at LYFE Institute restaurant, collecting feedback from 70 consumers over 2 weeks.
- The objective was to validate the sensory improvements implemented by the chefs on the recipe and check the overall appreciation of the dessert by French consumers.
- Results demonstrated that the chokeberry increase in cheesecake didn’t impact on the overall liking score, despite a slightly too acidic/lack of sweetness sensory profile. Crispy apple chips were really liked.
- The InHort team was supporting the questionnaire redaction, test organisation, data analysis and report redaction, as well as the presentation.

3.6.2. Data analysis and open-ended question analysis

- PhD researchers were invited to learn how to analyse open comments from consumers, collecting the main words related to each product.
- They learnt how to build up a contingency table of verbatims, vocabulary used by consumers and how to present that data in a reporting way for the presentation of the research to a wide team.

3.6.3. Data Analysis & Reporting

- Analysing and interpreting consumer test data, including statistical evaluation of results.
- Reporting redaction and oriented toward answering the objective.

4. SATISFACTION FEEDBACK

While no formal feedback tools were used, InHort teams consistently expressed high satisfaction with the training sessions, as reflected in post-training discussions (seminars for the InHort community) and internal feedback meetings. These exchanges highlighted not only enhanced confidence but also a strong sense of achievement among participants.

Through hands-on exposure to sensory description techniques and consumer research processes, visiting researchers and scientists upgraded their analytical and methodological skills. This experience empowered them to identify challenges proactively, adapt research plans with flexibility, and apply their newfound expertise with greater assurance and precision. The training fostered both individual growth and team cohesion, ensuring readiness for future projects.

5. DEVIATIONS, CHALLENGES & MITIGATION STRATEGIES

Study Visit ID	Challenges	Mitigation Strategies	Deviations (yes/no)
T2.1 - SV-001	The recruitment of panelists was challenged by the short period of execution.	We allowed for flexibility in the scheduling of panelists and thus obtained enough panelists for high quality studies.	No deviations
T2.1 - SV-002	Same as above	Same as above	No deviations
T2.2 - SV-001	During the 1st focus group, it would have been good to received ingredients in advance and to allow ingredients tasting to consumers to better enhance co-creation.	Explanation and description of ingredients sensory characteristics made by InHort researchers.	No deviations

T2.2 - SV-002	The recipes texture and taste not adapted to French consumers. 4 recipes developed which could be too much.	Usage test of side food to be used to consume the products, but not a proper a liking evaluation. Pre-test of each recipe helping to decrease number of products to be tasted during the test.	Yes Change of participant of the study visit compared to the original plan presented in Milestone 2
T2.3 - SV-001	No specific challenge observed: everything went well, the products arrived on time, recruitment was anticipated	No mitigation strategy needed	No deviations
T2.3 - SV-002	Questionnaire too long for the chosen methodology. Rather hard recruitment of consumers since imposed dessert.	The drop of answers caused by the challenges led to an extension of fieldwork days to complete the required number of consumers answers for each product.	No deviations

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

For recruitment delays, maintain a flexible schedule and extend fieldwork days early on to secure enough participants.

To improve co-creation, ensure ingredients arrive in advance to allow tasting by the focus group participants and provide detailed sensory descriptions to help consumers engage effectively.

Shorten questionnaires and pre-test them to avoid dropouts and compensate for lower response rates by extending data collection periods.

7. ANNEXES

Study Visit ID	Documents title	Description of content	LINK to SharePoint document
T2.1 - SV-001 / 002	IP_sensory_test_checklist PM	Checklist template for execution of Projective Mapping	IP_sensory_test_checklist PM.xlsx
T2.1 - SV-001 / 002	IP Report DescAnalysis UK	Template for initial reporting of outcome, that the visitors can use to develop their reports.	IP Report DescAnalysis UK.docx
T2.2 - SV-001	Project HortiFood - WP2_2.2 - Lyfe Institute Culinary session report - WP2.2	Report of visits of InHort team in January 2025; qualitative research with culinary co-creation of recipes and sensory assessment in qualitative research. Report relating the culinary session and recipes developed based on consumer's ideation	Project HortiFood - WP2_2.2 - Lyfe Institute.pptx Culinary session report - WP2.2.pdf

T2.2 - SV-002	Quick report_usage test on spreads_July2025	Report describing the usage test which took place in LYFE Institute in July 2025 on pastes developed by InHort team: behaviour observation and side food usage to consume the products	Quick report_usage test on spreads_July2025.pptx
T2.3 - SV-001	Program WP2 ESA WP2.3 Internship ESA	Agenda of June visit in ESA Presented topics are detailed and skills/knowledge are developed.	Program WP2 ESA.xlsx WP2.3 Internship ESA.docx
T2.3 - SV-002	WP2.3 - Report Quantitative Research	This report issued by the InHort team and LYFE team is a complete overview of the quantitative research run on the selected recipe out from WP2.2 - SV-001, with vocabulary analysis, quantitative data analysed, methodology review and improvement feedback.	WP2.3 - Report Quantitative Research.pptx
PANGBORN	Pangborn Poster	Poster presentation of the HFT project including each step of the project: qualitative research with consumers on ingredients and recipes ideation, culinary development and sensory qualitative feedback from consumers, recipe selection and quantitative research to get consumer's feedback.	Poster Pangborn - Finale version-2.pdf